

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF LIGANDS AND COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Decomp. temp °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)			
			C	H	N	Metal
C ₁₀ H ₁₁ NO ₂	White	142	66.96 (67.04)	7.12 (7.26)	7.12 (7.82)	—
Cu(C ₁₀ H ₁₂ NO ₂) ₂	Buff	278	57.50 (57.28)	5.60 (5.72)	6.70 (6.67)	15.25 (15.13)
Ni(C ₁₀ H ₁₂ NO ₂) ₂	Green	~300	57.90 (57.87)	5.75 (5.78)	6.70 (6.75)	14.20 (14.15)
Co(C ₁₀ H ₁₂ NO ₂) ₂	Brown	230	57.50 (57.84)	5.60 (5.78)	6.50 (6.74)	14.10 (14.19)
Mn(C ₁₀ H ₁₂ NO ₂) ₂	Brownish black	250	58.25 (58.39)	5.75 (5.83)	6.75 (6.81)	13.30 (13.38)
Pd(C ₁₀ H ₁₂ NO ₂) ₂	Yellow	286	51.90 (51.98)	5.19 (5.30)	6.05 (6.12)	23.00 (23.50)
VO(C ₁₀ H ₁₂ NO ₂) ₂	Grey	178d	56.70 (56.73)	5.65 (5.67)	6.60 (6.61)	12.20 (12.05)
UO ₂ (C ₁₀ H ₁₂ NO ₂) ₂	Orange	205	38.30 (38.33)	3.75 (3.83)	4.40 (4.47)	38.00 (38.02)
C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₂	Brown	55	73.25 (73.17)	7.25 (7.31)	—	—
UO ₂ (C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂) ₂	Orange	195	40.06 (40.26)	3.50 (3.69)	—	40.00 (39.94)

${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2A_1$ transition or to the low energy charge transfer and inter-ligand transition. This complex appears to be five-coordinate with O of the vanadyl group lying at the apex of a square based pyramid, N and O of the ligand forming the basal plane.

The observed magnetic moment (5.86 B.M.) of the Mn^{II}-HDMAOX indicates five unpaired electrons. The d^5 -configuration being spherically symmetrical, the ground state suffers no change in the stereochemistry. Both the octahedral and the tetrahedral d^5 ions have the same order of energy levels. The 17 200, 18 750, 20 000, 21 200, 22 450 and 27 500 cm^{-1} bands in the complex correspond to the transitions ${}^6A_1 \rightarrow {}^4T_1(G)$, ${}^6A_1 \rightarrow {}^4T_2(G)$, ${}^6A_1 \rightarrow {}^4E(D)$, ${}^6A_1 \rightarrow {}^4T_2(D)$, ${}^6A_1 \rightarrow {}^4E(D)$ and ${}^6A_1 \rightarrow {}^4E(D)$ respectively. The tetrahedral nature of the complex has been confirmed on the basis of its molar absorbance value⁶.

Infrared spectra: The ir spectra of the ligands show strong bands at 3 380 (OH chelated), 3 240 (OH for N-OH), 2 920, 2 850 (CH of methylene groups) and 1 640 cm^{-1} (C-N).

The ir spectra of the chelates show that the phenolic hydrogen is replaced by the metal as the band at 3 380 cm^{-1} (OH chelated) disappears in the complexes. The strong band at 1 640 cm^{-1} (C-N) shifts from 20–10 cm^{-1} to lower frequency in the metal chelates indicating that N of the =N-OH group coordinates with the metal ion in case of HDMAOX. The $\nu_{\text{N-O}}$ band at 980 cm^{-1} in the ligand HDMAOX shifts to 974–960 cm^{-1} in the chelates, a position recommended by various workers^{7,8}. The bands at 990 and 935 cm^{-1} correspond to $\nu_{\text{N-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{O-U=O}}$ respectively⁹. The bands at 515–550 and 550–590 cm^{-1} indicate M-O and M-N bands respectively¹⁰, which may also be coupled with the ligand bands.

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Spectrophotometric Study on some Palladium(II) Hydrazopyrazolone Complexes

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METAL complexes of azopyrazolone compounds are of great importance in technical dye chemistry^{1,2}. They are more resistant to chemical reagents than the metal-free dyes. Complex formation has a favourable effect on the stability of the azo bridge³. Also, colour of the azo compounds is greatly

affected if one of the azo nitrogens coordinates to a metal ion.

Snavelly *et al.*⁴ prepared a series of complexes of divalent metal ions with *o*-hydroxy-, *o*-carboxy- and *o,o'*-dihydroxypyrazolone compounds and determined their stability constants. Kozyrev *et al.*⁵ studied the formation of monoazodye complexes of some transition metal cations spectrophotometrically. Complexation was associated with a bathochromic shift in the absorption maximum with respect to the uncomplexed ligands.

The present paper describes a spectrophotometric estimation of Pd^{II} with three arylhydrazopyrazolone dyes and determination of stability constants of the Pd^{II} complexes with these ligands.

Experimental

Palladium(II) chloride, *o*-aminophenol, 2-amino-4-chlorophenyl, 2-amino-4-methylphenol, ethyl acetoacetate, sodium hydroxide and dioxane were all of reagent grade. Dioxane was dried using sodium metal and lithium aluminium hydride, then distilled and the fraction in the b.p. range 100.5–101° was collected.

Preparation of organic ligands: 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone was synthesised by the reaction of ethylacetoacetate and phenylhydrazine⁶. The crude product was recrystallised from alcohol-water mixture and colourless crystals were obtained. Phenylazopyrazolones were prepared by coupling 1-phenyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone with the diazonium salt of the corresponding amine in the presence of sodium acetate. The crude products were recrystallised from acetic acid (Table 1).

Preparation of solutions: Pd^{II} chloride solutions (2×10^{-2} and 5×10^{-3} M) were prepared by dissolving the salt in water and adding dilute HCl acid to ensure complete dissolution. Palladium content was determined gravimetrically as its dimethylglyoxime complex⁷. Solutions of the organic ligands (1.25×10^{-2} and 5×10^{-3} M) were prepared in purified dioxane.

pH measurements were made with a China 25 pH-meter (accuracy ± 0.02 pH unit). The visible spectra were recorded at room temperature with a Perkin-Elmer 550 S spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

The nature of Pd^{II} complexes: The acid form of 2-hydroxy ligands are represented as follows:

- 1, X = H
- 2, X = CH₃
- 3, X = Cl

It was also shown⁸ that the free ligand ionises in two steps due to deprotonation of the phenolic group (pH < 9) and the second step is the ionisation of the hydrazo proton (pH > 10). The colours of H₂L, HL⁻, L²⁻ are orange, red and yellow, respectively.

Beer's law was found to be obeyed up to [Pd^{II}] = 9×10^{-5} M for ligands 1, 2 and 3, respectively, which show that these Pd^{II}-ligand complexes can be used for the spectrophotometric determination of micro amounts of Pd^{II}. The best pH range was found to be pH 4–6 when the solutions are red due to the formation of the Pd^{II} complexes.

The stoichiometry of the Pd^{II} complexes was studied by molar ratio⁹, continuous variation¹⁰, straight line¹¹, slope ratio¹² and limiting logarithmic¹³ methods and the results indicated the formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 metal-ligand, complexes.

The stability constants of the Pd^{II} complexes with ligands 1, 2 and 3 were calculated using the limiting logarithmic, Hymann and molar-ratio methods from which average log *K* values were found to be 17.16 ± 0.28 , 17.41 ± 0.21 and 15.85 ± 0.14 , respectively.

Spectrophotometric titration of Pd^{II} with EDTA using 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-(2-phenylazo)-5-pyrazolones as indicators: In a series of 10-ml measuring flasks containing 5×10^{-3} M Pd^{II} solution (0.5 ml), successive amounts of EDTA (0.1–0.9 ml; 5×10^{-3} M), 5×10^{-3} M ligand in dioxane (2 ml) and 0.2 M acetate buffer (pH = 5; 1.3 ml) were added and then

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND M.P. DATA OF LIGANDS

Sl no.	Compd.	Analysis %: Found/(Calcd.)				M.p °C
		C	H	N	Cl	
1.	1-Phenyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone	69.3 (69.0)	6.0 (5.8)	15.5 (16.0)	—	126.7 ^a
2	1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-(2-hydroxyphenylhydrazo)-5-pyrazolone (1)	65.4 (65.3)	5.1 (4.8)	18.2 (19.0)	—	236.7
3.	1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-(2-hydroxy-5-methylphenylhydrazo)-5-pyrazolone (2)	66.4 (66.2)	5.2 (5.7)	17.7 (18.1)	—	224.5
4.	1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-(2-hydroxy-5-chlorophenylhydrazo)-5-pyrazolone (3)	58.7 (58.5)	4.2 (4.0)	16.7 (17.0)	10.7 (10.8)	256.0

^aLit 127.0° (Ref. 1).

completed to the mark with dioxane. The spectra of the solutions were recorded against reagent blank. An example of the spectra is represented in Fig. 1,

Fig. 1. Spectrophotometric titration of Pd^{II} with EDTA using 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-(2-hydroxyphenylazo)-5-pyrazolone, (1) as indicator.

in the case of using ligand 1 as an indicator. The absorbances of the different solutions at several wavelengths for the three ligands are plotted against the volume of EDTA and are shown in Fig. 2. Thus, micrograms of Pd^{II} can be determined with fair accuracy. However, it was observed that the spectrum does not vanish as in the case with other transition metals. This may be due to the absorbance of the newly formed Pd^{II}-EDTA complex. So, it is recommended that the measurements can be continued till the absorbance becomes constant.

Fig. 2. Spectrophotometric titration of Pd^{II} using the ligands as indicators: (A) 1, (B) 2 and (C) 3.

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Effect of Pyrosulphate Fusion on the Oxidation State of Platinum Group Metals†

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TRACE amounts of rhodium are generally determined by spectrophotometric methods using stannous chloride¹ or bromide² or by d.c. polarography³ by the reduction of Rh^{III}-pyridine complex. Standard rhodium solutions are prepared⁴ by fusing rhodium metal with potassium pyrosulphate. However, it is observed that during fusion of Rh⁰ or RhCl₃.xH₂O with K₂S₂O₇, rhodium is oxidised to quinequivalent state. Pyrosulphate-induced oxidation of rhodium or other platinum group metals during fusion has not been reported so far. While the determination of traces of rhodium by spectrophotometric methods after fusion with K₂S₂O₇ may give accurate results, its estimation by differential pulse polarography method leads to serious errors because of the change in the oxidation state of the metal. Experimental evidence for the oxidation of rhodium (or other platinum group) metal(s) or metal salts during fusion with K₂S₂O₇-polarographic, coulometric and ESCA, is presented here.

Experimental

The method followed to estimate traces of rhodium by differential pulse polarography was essentially the same as described by Willis³ for rhodium estimation by d.c. polarography. A 100 ppm rhodium standard solution was prepared by fusing 10 mg of finely divided rhodium metal (99.99% purity, Johnson Matthey) with 1 or 2 g of potassium pyrosulphate in a silica crucible until it was brought into solution. The melt was dissolved in 1 N sulphuric acid and diluted to 100 ml with the same acid. Aliquots from this stock solution in 1M

pyridine and 1M KCl were polarogrammed after purging the solution with oxygen-free nitrogen using a PAR 174A polarographic analyser over the range 0 to -1.5 V (vs Ag/AgCl). The expected well-defined peak at -0.414 V was however not observed. The same aliquots, however, after fuming with concentrated HCl several times and complexed with 1M pyridine containing 1M KCl, gave well-defined differential pulse polarographic peak at -0.46 V (vs Ag/AgCl). The working range was found to be 1-10 ppm (Table 1).

TABLE 1—DIFFERENTIAL PULSE POLAROGRAPHY OF Rh-PYRIDINE COMPLEX IN 1M KCl

Peak potentials (E_p) = -0.46 V (vs Ag/AgCl), Scan rate = 2 mV s⁻¹, modulation amplitude 50 mV and scan range 0 to -1.5 V.

Conc. of Rh ppm	i_p (μ A)	
	A	B
1.00	0.98	1.97
2.00	1.98	3.93
3.00	2.96	5.89
4.00	3.90	7.79
5.00	4.94	9.86
6.00	5.88	11.80
7.00	6.85	13.68
8.00	7.88	15.74
9.00	8.83	17.70
10.00	9.82	19.66

A = RhCl₃.xH₂O unfused and unfumed. B = Rh metal or RhCl₃.xH₂O fused and fumed.

The anionic rhodium(v) complex as its tetrabutylammonium salt (C₄H₉)₄N[RhI₆] was isolated by mixing aqueous solutions of the fused product (pale pink colour) and tetrabutylammonium iodide (Found: C, 17.63; H, 4.07; N, 1.76; Rh, 10.46. Calcd. for C₁₆H₃₆NRhI₆: C, 17.35; H, 3.28; N, 1.27; Rh, 9.3%). Binding energy of Rh 3d_{5/2}, 313.8 eV, 313.4 eV. Other platinum group metal chlorides, K₂PtCl₄, K₂PdCl₄, RuCl₃ and IrCl₃.xH₂O were fused with K₂S₂O₇ and treated similarly. The binding energies (in eV) of the metals in the products (Pt 4f_{7/2}, 75.4; Pd 3d_{5/2}, 340.0; 339.46; Ir 4f_{7/2}, 64.16; Ru 3d_{5/2}, 281.9) confirm that these metals undergo oxidation to higher valent state during fusion with K₂S₂O₇-Pt^{II} and Pd^{II} to Pt^{IV} and Pd^{IV}, Ru^{III} and Ir^{III} to possibly Ru^V and Ir^V.

Results and Discussion

The differential pulse polarogram peak heights of rhodium solutions (same concentrations prepared from RhCl₃.xH₂O and analysed spectrophotometrically and by AAS) were exactly half the heights of the standards prepared via fusing rhodium metal with K₂S₂O₇ and later fumed with concentrated HCl. In other words, the peak heights of solutions of rhodium metal fused with K₂S₂O₇ and later fumed with concentrated HCl and the pure RhCl₃.xH₂O solution in 1 M pyridine and KCl were in the ratio 2 : 1. Furthermore, the peak heights of the solutions (same concentration) of RhCl₃.xH₂O

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